

JOINT DESIGN OF CONTINUOUS/DISCONTINUOUS HYBRID CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an investigation into co-compression moulding of discontinuous fibre compounds with continuous fibre plies, to create a hybrid laminate. The tensile strength and stiffness of a hybrid composite containing 20% (by vol.) UD fibre were shown to be 110% and 60% higher, respectively, than the baseline discontinuous compound, when the UD fibres were aligned in the primary loading direction.

The aim of this work was to investigate the effect of different ply layouts in the transition zone from the continuous fibre plies to the discontinuous fibre material, by determining the flexural performance and Mode-I fracture toughness. Synchronising the UD ply ends significantly reduces the flexural strength of the hybrid laminate to around 66% of the strength of the discontinuous compound. Results therefore indicate that the continuous-discontinuous joint design requires stepping or tapering of the continuous fibre plies to achieve an interface angle of less than 7° in order to reduce the peel stress. Fracture toughness values indicate that the discontinuous architecture improves the overall fracture toughness of the system by up to 23%, and 37% improvement to crack initiation load, due to 'fibre bridging' which suppresses crack development.

1 INTRODUCTION

Compression moulding offers the fastest route for manufacturing composite components from thermoset matrices, with sheet moulding compounds (SMC) being the most widely used form of fibre reinforced composites within the automotive industry. Whilst the discontinuous nature of these moulding compounds limits the stiffness and strength compared to continuous fibre composites, the Takt time is typically 5-10 minutes (depending on part thickness), which makes them suitable for production volumes approaching 50,000ppa. However, carbon fibre moulding compounds have largely remained unexploited due to high material costs, as they tend to be derived from UD prepregs. A recent paper by the authors [1] has demonstrated a novel method for producing discontinuous carbon fibre moulding compounds using a robotic deposition process. Directed Fibre Compounding (DFC) simultaneously sprays low viscosity liquid epoxy resin and discontinuous carbon fibre bundles to create a charge, using the constituent materials in their cheapest form. This produces a low-cost material with similar properties to prepreg-derived carbon fibre / epoxy moulding compounds [2, 3].

The addition of local continuous UD fibre plies to the discontinuous DFC architecture has the potential to enhance the mechanical performance of this material further, making it suitable for structural applications [4]. It is impractical to cover large areas of the compression mould tool with continuous fibres for complex components because of the increase in charge preparation time, so hybridising offers additional local reinforcement using highly optimised fibre architectures. Consequently, this introduces a complex stress state between the two architectures at the transition point from one material to another, which can lead to large reductions in mechanical performance. When the end of a ply is positioned internally within a stack, a triangular resin rich region is formed at the ply drop, introducing a potential failure initiation site. There are a number of ply drop design guidelines that can be adopted to maximise strength and avoid delamination [5-8]:

- Surface plies should not be dropped
- The maximum taper angle, α (**Fig 1**), should not exceed 7°. Ply drops should therefore be staggered by a minimum distance of approximately eight times the thickness of the ply.

- Ply drops should be staggered through the thickness, alternating between plies close to the surface and close to the laminate centre line
- Plies should be dropped in decreasing order of stiffness to ensure smooth transfer of load and reduce stress concentrations. For example, 0° plies first and 90° plies last.
- The number of plies dropped at any location should be kept to a minimum to reduce the volume of resin rich regions.

The most significant variable affecting the performance of a joint is the distance between each step [5]. The optimal number of plies ending at any particular step should be just one, as increasing this number significantly reduces the tensile and flexural performance [9]. Other joint design guidelines for composites often suggest tapering the ends of the composite, usually by machining the end of the moulded laminate to form a scarf joint, if the laminate cannot be easily stepped during the layup. This minimises the shear stress distribution at the joint interface, commonly referred to as the 'peel stress' [7, 8, 10]. The peel stress is a function of the thickness of each joint constituent [11]. A shallower taper angle, or larger step size, will minimise the thickness distribution along the joint length and therefore minimise the peel stress at the thinnest point, where delamination is most likely to initiate.

Failure within hybrid composites can occur within three distinct regions; the continuous fibre plies, the discontinuous fibre material and the interface between plies or architectures. Failure within the continuous plies requires breakage of the high strength fibres and therefore requires the highest stress. Within discontinuous fibre composites, stress concentrations often arise at the ends of the fibre bundles [12, 13]. For shorter fibre lengths, fibre pull-out increasingly dominates the fracture mechanism as a result of a smaller contact area with the matrix. Thus, there is more fibre breakage with longer fibre lengths since the larger fibre-matrix interface requires greater loads to overcome the interfacial adhesion [14]. Failure at the interface in the form of delamination, is dominated by the performance of the resin between the plies or architectures. During mode-I separation, delamination is induced along an interface, where a resin rich interface provides a low strength path where a crack may propagate [15]. However, load carrying fibres near to, or interleaving the interface, transfer stress across the interface producing a stress distribution surrounding the crack tip. Over the length of this damage zone, broken or pulled out fibres no longer contribute to stress transfer. This reduces the ability to analyse the fracture as a linear elastic fracture mechanism [14].

Commonly for discontinuous fibre architectures, cracks propagating perpendicular to a fibre bundle result in crack arresting or non-linear crack growth, as it deviates around the high strength fibres. The crack deflection produces fibre bridging across the interface which gives excellent toughness during mode-I separation [16]. However, cracks propagating parallel to a fibre experience less crack deflection and bridging. This prevents load transfer across the interface and therefore reduces toughness. Fibre bridging remains the most efficient mechanism for reducing the stress level at the crack, by transferring the stress through the bridged fibres across the interface [17]. A study by Truss et al. [16] demonstrates that fibre bridging leads to higher fracture toughness for discontinuous fibre materials (981 J/m²) compared to continuous fibre material (250 J/m²).

This paper characterises the change in mechanical performance achieved by co-compression moulding DFC with UD carbon fibre non-crimp fabrics. Initially, the influence of the volume ratio of UD to DFC within symmetric arrangements (UD/DFC/UD) is determined. However, the main focus of the paper is understanding the effect of the laminate design in the transition zone between these dissimilar architectures, in terms of ply step size and the ply drop strategy. These are investigated in terms of the bending and tensile performance of the joint and evaluated by through-thickness strain maps for each joint arrangement. The fracture toughness of discontinuous and continuous carbon fibre/epoxy composite benchmarks is also investigated in addition to the hybrid architectures to highlight the dominant fracture mechanisms during mode-I separation. The benefit of compression moulding hybrid laminates rather than pre-curing the continuous plies prior to compression moulding is also demonstrated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Discontinuous fibre compound (DFC) was produced using the methodology outlined by Evans et al. [1]. T700 12K carbon fibre tows were chopped to a fibre length of 25mm and a four-component epoxy resin from Huntsman was used: Resin XU 3508, Aradur 1571, Accelerator 1573 and Hardener 3403. The target fibre volume fraction for the charge was 50%. The NCF was a UD carbon fibre with multiaxial E-glass stitching, at 90° and ±45°. The NCF consisted of 24K tows with an areal density of 375gsm.

The tensile performance of the hybrid plaques was benchmarked against monolithic DFC and UD plaques. The volume content of DFC and 0° UD fabric was varied in each of the hybrid carbon fibre plaques, whilst maintaining a 3mm thickness. The percentage volume content of UD was 0% (DFC only), 20%, 40%, 60% 80% and 100% (UD only). The UD plies were positioned at the upper and lower tool surface (UD/DFC/UD) to minimise the out-of-plane ply waviness and to ensure a thicker DFC central section compared to dividing the DFC material into a DFC/UD/DFC sandwich configuration. This helped to reduce any potential size effects previously observed when moulding thin discontinuous fibre architectures [18].

The joint design was divided into two studies: step size and ply drop arrangement. First, the effect of step size was considered for a *stepped* geometry (**Fig. 1a**). Stepped joints were arranged so that each ply was incrementally shorter than the surface ply. The step length was increased from 0 mm (all ply ends synchronised) to 1.5mm, 3mm, 6mm and 12mm. A second study was conducted using two additional types of joint design to investigate the effect of the ply drop arrangement (shown by **Fig. 1**). These were *tapered* and *alternating* joints. Tapered joints had the longest UD ply positioned at the interface with the discontinuous fibres, which encased the ends of each of the other UD plies. The alternating arrangement had the longest ply positioned at the tool surface, which was a combination of a stepped and tapered joint. The step size for all three geometries was kept constant at 6mm (20 times the ply thickness). Each of these joints were configured with 7 plies of 0° UD fabric, which were placed on top of a DFC charge with uniform areal density covering 100% of the tool surface. This was to minimise the level of charge flow in the vicinity of the transition zone.

Figure 1: Schematic of the joint geometries between UD laminates in the zero orientation (dark grey) and random DFC (light grey): (a) stepped, (b) tapered and (c) alternating. α is the taper angle

Figure 2: Schematic of the location of the load roller during 3-point bend when testing in the (a) positive bending direction and (b) the negative bending direction

The in-plane and out-of-plane mechanical performance were characterised during both studies by performing tensile and three-point bending at the centre of each joint. Three-point bend testing was also performed in both the positive and negative bending directions (**Fig. 2**), where the UD material was positioned on the upper or lower surfaces respectively.

A double cantilevered beam (DCB) test was used to measure the mode-I fracture toughness of both the DFC and UD materials (independently) and the hybrid fibre architecture [0₅/DFC], separated at the planar interface between the dissimilar material. Two variations of the hybrid architecture interface were investigated. The first was produced by co-compression moulding the continuous and discontinuous components, using 100% tool coverage for both materials. The second was produced by pre-curing the UD plies in an oven under vacuum pressure before compression moulding with the DFC, preventing matrix crosslinking at the interface. The thickness of the DFC component was chosen to give an equal bending stiffness to the UD element, to ensure that delamination occurred horizontally at the interface between the two materials.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 In-plane properties of hybrid fibre architecture

Hybrid composite plaques were manufactured with an increasing percentage of unidirectional carbon fibre. The tensile stiffness and strength (**Fig. 3**) both follow strong linear relationships in the longitudinal and transverse orientations. Consequently, there is good agreement between the experimental data and rule of mixtures predictions. The baseline strength of 333MPa \pm 22MPa for the isotropic DFC material (0% UD) increases by more than 110% with only 20% UD content, but the corresponding transverse strength reduces by just 25%.

Figure 3: (a) Tensile modulus and (b) strength of UD/DFC hybrid carbon fibre architecture with increasing percentage of UD fabric by volume. Linear dotted lines indicate predictions by rule of mixtures (RoM)

3.2 Joint design: Effect of step size

Mechanical Performance

Micrographs for varying step sizes (**Fig. 4**) show the through-thickness interface between the unidirectional plies and the discontinuous DFC. There is significant ‘swirling’ of the discontinuous fibres for a UD step size of 0mm (**Fig. 4a**), which results in varying fibre content within the discontinuous region. The discontinuous material is initially thicker and therefore experiences higher compressive forces at a shorter stroke during the compression stage. This results in DFC material flowing towards the thicker sections of the compound (from right to left in the micrographs). Similar swirling was also observed in a previous study [1] when the charge coverage was reduced to just 40% of the tool area, but it is exacerbated here as the discontinuous fibres are encouraged to flow over a steep change in gradient at the end of the UD ply stack. This gradient is reduced as the step size increases, therefore this reduces the observed levels of turbulence in the DFC material, as shown in **Fig. 4b** and

Fig. 4c. A resin rich region was also noted at the end of each ply drop. The shape of the resin rich region varies depending on the orientation of the discontinuous fibre bundle that bridges the end of the continuous fibre ply.

Flexural properties of the stepped joints have been compared to the baseline DFC (**Fig. 5**). The flexural modulus increases linearly with increasing step size. The ratio of step size to ply thickness (S-T ratio) needs to be greater than 5:1 (step length of 1.5mm), to maintain a higher flexural modulus than the DFC material. However, the flexural strength required an S-T ratio greater than 20:1 (step length of 6mm) to exceed the baseline flexural strength of the DFC.

Figure 4: Micrographs (5x magnification) of stepped unidirectional/discontinuous carbon fibre joints produced by co-compression moulding: (a) 0mm, (b) 1.5mm and (c) 3mm step sizes. Point 1 indicates fibre swirling and Points 2 and 3 indicate some locations of resin richness at the end of each ply drop.

Figure 5: Flexural properties of UD/DFC stepped joints in positive and negative bending directions for varying step size. N.b. negative bending points are offset by +0.25mm for clarity. DFC baseline at 32.4GPa \pm 4.6 modulus and 435.5MPa \pm 60.4 strength.

Although there was no significant difference between the positive and negative bending directions in terms of flexural modulus, the flexural strengths (**Fig. 5b**) were affected due to a change in failure mechanism. During positive bending, the UD fibres on the upper surface were in compression and failure occurred due to tension in the DFC material. For shorter step sizes, < 6mm, it was observed that most failures occurred away from the joint because of the non-uniform bending moment caused by the asymmetric laminate (**Fig. 6a**). As the step size increased, the failure region moved closer to the load point, exhibiting buckling in the UD laminates and some delamination (**Fig. 6c**). However, in negative

bending tension in the UD fibres increased the stress in the resin rich region at the end of the surface laminate. As this resin rich region fails, the crack propagates along the boundary between the continuous and discontinuous fibres (**Fig. 6b and 6d**). This change in failure mechanism reduced the flexural strength by approximately 50MPa in the negative bending direction compared to the positive direction.

Figure 6: Examples of failure mechanisms for step size 5:1 (1.5mm) in (a) positive and (b) negative bending directions, and step size 20:1 (6mm) in (c) positive (c) and (d) negative bending directions.

When the hybrid plaques were subjected to an axial load, it was found that the effects of the joint size were significant. The tensile modulus exceeds that of DFC ($36.3\text{GPa} \pm 3.3\text{GPa}$) with an S-T ratio of just 5:1 (step length of 1.5mm). However, the ultimate tensile strengths (**Fig. 7**) for the hybrids with stepped joints are significantly lower than the DFC baseline ($323\text{MPa} \pm 27\text{MPa}$). This reduction in strength is the result of the resin rich regions that form at the end of the surface UD ply, which are the site for crack initiation. However, there is a distinguishable trend with increasing step length as the taper angle reduces, which reduces the stress concentration at the end of each ply and facilitates a more gradual transition from high stiffness to low stiffness material. The peel stress and the associated tensile stress at the end of the UD surface ply decrease with increasing step size. The crack propagates along the resin rich path along the joint interface at the end of each ply step (**Fig. 8**).

Figure 7: Tensile strength and modulus of UD/DFC stepped joints for varying step size.

Out-of-plane strains were evident in the laminate when in-plane tensile loads were applied, due to the asymmetry of the layup. This caused failure at lower tensile strengths than expected, i.e. lower than the tensile strength of the DFC. This was investigated further using electronic speckle pattern interferometry (ESPI).

Figure 8: Time stepped images of joint specimen (step size = 0mm) showing the specimen at the start of the test (0s), crack initiation (22s), sudden crack propagation (36s) and total failure (47s)

ESPI strain measurements

ESPI was performed initially to investigate the strain distribution on the front and back faces of the stepped joint specimens. The strains across the width of the specimen were uniform on each side, but the magnitude of the strain on the DFC surface (rear) was approximately 4 times higher than the strain recorded on the UD surface (front) at an applied load of 5kN. These dissimilar strains imply that there is shear through the thickness of the sample and therefore the sample is not loaded in pure tension. It is clear from the out-of-plane ESPI images (**Fig. 9**) that the specimen asymmetry induces bending when a tensile load is applied. The tensile strengths presented in **Fig. 7** are therefore artificially low.

According to the ESPI results (**Fig. 9**), the ends of the surface ply experienced a large axial strain because of the resin rich region in this location. This is the reason failure initiates from the surface at the interface between the continuous and discontinuous fibre architecture. The largest of these axial strains is seen within the 'No Step' specimen where all ply ends are synchronised (**Fig. 4a**). **Fig. 9** indicates that the size and magnitude of the axial strain at the end of the surface ply reduces dramatically from approximately 33 microstrain to 8 microstrain (for an applied load of 5 kN) as the step size increases from 0 mm to 3 mm (S-T ratio of 10:1). As the step size increases further, the magnitude of the maximum axial strain at the surface remains at approximately 8 microstrain for a 5 kN load. This agrees with the joint design guidelines, which suggest that the joint angle should not exceed 7° [8, 10], supporting the conclusion that the S-T ratio must be greater than 8:1.

When comparing ESPI strain results to the failure locations of the specimens, the axial strains at the end of the plies were the dominate cause of failure when the S-T ratio was less than or equal 10:1 ($\leq 3\text{mm}$), resulting in failure at the joint for every specimen. However, failure within the DFC material commonly occurred for S-T ratios greater than or equal to 20:1 ($\geq 6\text{mm}$), due to through-thickness shear.

3.3 Joint design: Effect of joint geometry

The design of the joint (stepped, tapered or alternating (**Fig. 1**)) was varied to change the position of the ends of the dropped plies in relation to the interface. The aim was to reduce the concentration of ply ends near to the DFC/UD interface to deflect crack growth. The tapered and alternating arrangements only had one and two ply drops at the DFC/UD interface, respectively. The remaining plies were all enclosed by other plies.

The flexural modulus of the tapered and alternating geometries (**Fig. 10a**) are compared to those of the stepped joints. Tapering the joint provides a 'smoother' transition for the discontinuous architecture compared to a stepped joint, where the interface is more continuous in comparison to the steep gradients that form at the end of each ply within the stepped joints. Therefore, as the discontinuous fibre bundles

flow in the direction of the joint, less out-of-plane misalignment of the fibres is exhibited. This results in a statistically significant ($p < 1\%$) increase in the negative bending modulus from the stepped joint geometry to the tapered or alternating geometries. This is less apparent in the positive bending direction, but the trend is still statistically significant ($p < 5\%$), as the tapered joints have a greater flexural modulus than the stepped joints. According to the ultimate flexural strengths in **Fig. 10b**, joint design did not have a significant affect in positive bending. However, negative bending is largely influenced by crack deflection between the stress risers. All 7 ply ends are positioned at the joint interface for the stepped joint, whereas tapered joints only have one ply end at the joint interface, with the remaining ply ends at least one ply thickness away. The alternating joint contains 2 ply ends at the interface, but the others are up to 0.9mm (3 times the ply thickness) away from the interface. Within the alternating joints, the greatest number of continuous fibres therefore intersect any cracks that grow between the ply ends and the interface, preventing linear crack growth. This results in a statistically significant increase under negative bending ($p < 5\%$) compared with the stepped joints and alternating joints. Changing the geometry of the joint therefore reduces the difference between the positive and negative bending flexural strengths from 50MPa to approximately 10MPa. Additionally, although the increase in strength was small, it was sufficient to increase the flexural strength beyond the 436MPa baseline of the DFC material in both bending directions.

Figure 9: Through thickness axial (x-direction) and out-of-plane (z-direction) strain distributions (ESPI results with 60mm x 4mm view window, 5kN axial load) for each of the step size to ply thickness ratio: (a) No step, (b) 5:1, (c) 10:1, (d) 20:1 and (e) 40:1 (ply thickness - 0.3mm)

Figure 10: The flexural properties of UD-DFC joint with varying geometry compared to the DFC baseline (Modulus - 32.4GPa \pm 4.6 and Strength - 435.5MPa \pm 60.4).

There was no significant difference between the tensile moduli for the three geometries. However, the tensile strength increased by 7% when the joint design was changed from stepped to tapered (**Fig. 11**), from 199.5MPa \pm 17.7 to 213.2MPa \pm 11.3. ESPI results show no change in axial strain at the end of the surface ply from stepped to tapered (A1 in **Fig. 12**). However, enclosing all ply drops away from the joint interface reduces the axial strain concentration around the resin rich regions by around 50% compared to the stepped equivalent (A2 in **Fig. 12**). There is no significant difference between the strengths of the tapered and alternating joints, which are both approximately 210MPa.

Figure 11: Tensile strength of joint geometries and the modulus measured by extensometers

Figure 12: Through thickness axial, (x-direction), out-of-plane (z-direction) and shear strain (xz) distributions for tapered joint geometry with a 20:1 step size to ply thickness ratio (6mm)

3.4 Continuous/discontinuous interfacial Analysis

The interfacial properties of the hybrid laminates were analysed by investigating the mode-I fracture toughness by double cantilever beam (DCB) testing. The average crack initiation force was determined from the peak loads. For the non-hybrid benchmarks, the discontinuous material required approximately 34N more than the UD interface to initiate crack growth for the 25mm wide specimens (**Table 1**). The non-laminate structure of the discontinuous mesoscale architecture has a high resistance to crack initiation, indicated by the highest peak load recorded of all materials. A characteristic saw-tooth shape in the load-displacement curve is experienced (**Fig. 13**) because the random fibre architecture hinders crack propagation by a complex mixed failure mode at the crack front. Failure can occur in any resin rich regions at the interface, leading to sudden drops in load. It is possible for the crack to then encounter a bridging bundle at the interface, in which case the load rises sharply until bundle failure occurs (**Fig. 14b**). Fibre bridging across the crack therefore results in the largest mode-I fracture toughness, G_{IC} , over

the 100mm crack length (**Table 1**). G_{IC} is 23% higher for the DFC material than for the UD material which has a planar interface with no fibre bridging (**Fig 14a**). Energy is therefore released more progressively as the crack propagates at a continuous rate, indicated by the green line on the load-displacement curve (**Fig. 13**).

The crack initiation load for the co-moulded hybrid architecture is between the UD and DFC crack initiation loads. This implies that there is some interleaving of fibres at the interface, which disrupt the straight path for crack growth. As the bridged fibres fail the sudden release of energy results in high rate crack growth along the linear interface, similar to that observed for the DFC material. This results in a mode-I fracture toughness 11% lower than the UD plaque (**Table 1**). This interleaving however is eliminated if the UD material is pre-cured, as resin crosslinking is prevented between each of the materials and there is less disruption to the UD fibre architecture due to the moulding process. This scenario results in the least fibre bridging (**Fig 14d**) and therefore exhibits the smallest crack initiation load and mode-I fracture toughness, which are 35% and 40% lower, respectively, than the co-moulded equivalent (**Table 1**).

Interface		DFC	UD	Hybrid Architecture	
				Co-moulded	Pre-cured NCF
Crack Initiation Load	[N]	125.33	91.35	105.37	57.99
St. dev	[N]	14.37	1.70	13.77	6.75
CoV	[%]	11.46%	1.86%	13.07%	11.64%
Mode-I fracture toughness, G_{IC}	[J/m ²]	2689.78	2180.06	1940.85	1169.06
St. dev	[J/m ²]	469.24	143.13	117.71	154.50
CoV	[%]	17.45%	6.57%	6.06%	13.22%

Table 1: Average crack initiation loads and mode-I fracture toughness results from DCB testing

Figure 13: Typical load vs extension graphs of each of the DCB tests for each interface

4 CONCLUSIONS

The concept of hybridising discontinuous fibre composites with unidirectional materials has been studied as a potential solution for producing cost effective structural composite materials with short cycle times (5-10 minutes). Tensile testing has shown that the strength and stiffness of symmetrical hybrid laminates (UD/DFC/UD) increase linearly with increasing UD content according to a rule of mixtures relationship. Adding 20% by volume of UD fibres increases the tensile strength and modulus of the hybrid UD-DFC plaque by 110% and 60%, respectively, in the UD fibre direction.

The design of the joint was established to be of a significant factor when transitioning from a UD-DFC hybrid to a DFC only region. Micrographs were used to identify resin rich regions in the vicinity of the dropped ply ends. This was particularly apparent when all ply ends were synchronised, i.e. there was no step at the transition point between the UD and DFC. This observation was supported by the

strain distributions at the interface of the joint during axial loading. The strain concentration at the surface ply decreased with step size up to an S-T ratio of 10:1 (step length of 3mm). Greater step lengths exhibited a constant magnitude of strain in this region (approximately 8 microstrain with 5kN axial load) and the greatest strains were then experienced in the DFC part of the plaque. A 10:1 S-T ratio produced a joint angle of $\sim 6^\circ$, which agrees with the ply drop design guidelines that suggests that the taper angle should not exceed 7° ($\sim 8:1$ S-T ratio) [8, 10].

Figure 14: DCB tests of the (a) UD interface, (b) DFC centreline, (c) co-moulded UD-DFC hybrid fibre architecture and (d) hybrid fibre architecture where the UD material was pre-cured before compression moulding. Red markings are positioned every 5mm from the position of crack initiation.

Changing the joint geometry in order to move the dropped ply ends away from the joint interface was found to increase the bending strength in the negative direction (UD plies in tension on the underside). Introducing continuous fibres between the strain concentration at the end of the surface ply and the remaining plies, increased the stiffness of the interface which resulted in a more gradual transition from high to low stiffness materials. This subsequently reduced the out-of-plane strain within the joint region by 20% and therefore the local shear stress by approximately 50%.

The interfacial fracture toughness and crack initiation loads during mode-I separation of these hybrid plaques were influenced by the degree of fibre bridging, as a result of the discontinuous fibre bundles in the DFC material. This increases the load required to initiate the crack and the mode-I fracture toughness of the DFC by 37% and 23%, respectively, from that of a UD interface. The co-moulded hybrid architecture experiences a mixture of fibre bridging at regions of the discontinuous fibres interleaving the continuous plies and sudden energy release rates along the resin rich linear interface regions. This results in a crack initiation load between that of the UD and DFC materials but a lower overall fracture energy.

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